

FUNCTIONS AND COMPONENTS OF IMPROVISATION ABILITY IN FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

Kasimova O.A.

Gulistan State University Associate Doctorate

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12561535>

Abstract. *This article talks about the competence of pedagogical improvisation, the importance of pedagogical improvisation in the educational system, ways to implement improvisation in the work of a future primary school teacher.*

Key words: *elementary school, improvisation, pedagogical improvisation, character of improvisation, pedagogical communication, pedagogical creativity, creativity, criteria of improvisation.*

The modern trends of education development, the increase in professional requirements for the individual have increased the need to form the creative individuality of the teacher, to realize his creative abilities, and to develop the individual activity style. One of the components of creative activity is pedagogical improvisation. Experienced teachers have many techniques that can be used to solve various pedagogical problems during their career. But there are situations in which the teacher must make quick decisions, be flexible in non-standard situations in the classroom and extracurricular activities. [1, 54]

When developing a lesson plan, the teacher tries to clarify his views on the main components of the educational process: the goal, content, methods and tools to the maximum extent possible, formulates educational and cognitive tasks, clearly defines the organization of classes determines the methods, tries to predict and develop possible scenarios of the development of events and to find a way out of possible situations of pedagogical interaction with pupils and students, and changes the curriculum, or provides the possibility of rapid orientation in the real conditions of the educational process, that is, determines the ways of using pedagogical improvisation. The understanding of the topic explained by the teacher to students depends on many factors, not only the logic of the topic, but also the rules and conditions of learning, the place of study: classroom, equipment, emotional component, psychological climate and depends on others. All these factors make changes to the logic of the teacher education process. Personal qualities of the teacher play an important role in pedagogical activity. They help solve complex educational and educational problems. To do this, a teacher must have not only communication skills, but also creative thinking and imagination, concentration and motivation, flexibility and imagination, as well as many other qualities and characteristics of a person. The teacher is a “conductor” during the entire pedagogical interaction and controls all the processes that take place during the lesson. The teacher should always be ready to change and master the logic of the lesson, to direct it pedagogically in accordance with the effective education and upbringing of students.

Therefore, there is a natural need to find effective means of resolving conflicts between the pedagogical project of the lesson and the new, unexpected, suddenly arising circumstances of its implementation. It is a pedagogical improvisation, which acts as a kind of “regulator”, which should ensure that the teacher's ideas correspond to the real conditions of his creative well-being and the educational process. The improvisational nature of pedagogical activity creates the necessary conditions to meet the teacher's moral and psychological needs for success, professional

and personal growth, which is measured both by career growth and by rising to the highest level of skill and wisdom.

What is improvisation? In dictionaries, the concept of improvisation is etymologically related to elements of surprise and surprise. In fact, this is a creative process, which is also its result. There are musical, dance or other improvisations. Teachers use pedagogical improvisation in their work. How to choose a way in situations that arise suddenly or unexpectedly, improvisation is born here and now. This is a flow of creative activity that is not interrupted by criticism, judgment or assessment, that gives itself a form and direction, that flows "through" the author, that passes through him and finds time to observe the development of the theme and content.

Pedagogical improvisation (Latin *improvisus* - unexpected) is the teacher's ability to develop new solutions, as well as to quickly, flexibly and accurately respond to emerging pedagogical tasks.

All teachers use a certain scheme in their lessons. However, among them there are many who consider it appropriate to improvise - to deviate from the planned course of the lesson, to include in it unexpected, unprepared, sudden, here and now things.

The quality of education depends on the productivity of the previous stage and the results achieved at the current stage, the nature and size of the studied material, and the organizational and pedagogical impact on students [4, 74].

Students may be overly excited or interested in a foreign topic - so why not include it in the lesson, for example? Or, on the contrary, they may be bored, and then urgently need funds to pique their interest. There are teenagers who always like to ask questions or demonstrate their knowledge in class. In such cases, it is important to quickly and correctly recognize the reasons for such inclusions and respond to them with appropriate speed in order not to miss the opportunity to increase general interest in the subject of the lesson or, on the contrary, not to allow yourself and others.

Pedagogical improvisation is an integral part of pedagogical activity, which is born in the process of its direct implementation, without prior preparation, and represents the creative and often intuitive beginning of this activity. The teacher must act "on the road", make non-standard decisions and introduce new, newly invented elements into the pre-planned plan. Pedagogical improvisation is performed in public, in front of students, which in turn helps to create emergency situations. It can also be considered as a method of education and upbringing, because it has great opportunities for the development of children and the teacher himself. [2, 55]

In terms of defining the concept of pedagogical improvisation, we can say that it is the teacher's activity in the process of pedagogical communication without prior understanding. The goal of pedagogical improvisation is to find a completely new solution to problems in the specific conditions of pedagogical activity, and the essence of pedagogical improvisation is to quickly respond to emerging pedagogical tasks. This creativity is based on the interpretation of the lesson material being prepared in the conditions of the current activity, taking into account the real creative pedagogical attitude and feelings of the teacher.

Pedagogical improvisation is an effective tool for solving many pedagogical problems at all stages of the lesson and at all levels of pedagogical activity. According to Sokolnikov, "being able to see the tasks of one's activity in specific pedagogical conditions, to be able to determine their combination that needs to be solved at the moment is one of the most important aspects of the pedagogic art." [6, 288]

There are also four levels of pedagogical improvisation:

- improvisation at the level of educational communication;
- improvisation at the level of methodological reception;
- improvisation at the content level of the educational material;
- improvisation at the level of lesson goals.

Pedagogical improvisation can be implemented in various forms. This is a verbal action (the teacher's monologue or dialogue, humor, anecdote, analogy, etc.), physical action ("in its pure form" is very rare in the pedagogical process, but it is a gesture, a specific appearance, posture, etc.), can be verbal and physical actions (various jokes, games, mini-performances, etc.).

In this way, improvisation educates individuals who can unite in teams, who consider themselves independent and who are ready to take personal responsibility for the decisions made. It shows the general cultural level and personal qualities of the teacher (pedagogical technique, politeness, creative dominance, attention, imagination, research, inspiration, humor, etc.).

We briefly touched on the characteristics of pedagogical improvisation as a component of pedagogical creativity. Creative pedagogical activity depends on the conditions of the teacher's work, his own creative potential and well-being, the mood of the student group, the ability to implement and correct the pedagogical plan on time.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullayeva, Sh. Ro'ziyeva D.I. Pedagogik diagnostika va korreksiya. Darslik.- T.: Fan va texnologiyalar, 2019.-
2. Мягкая, Е. Б. Роль педагогической импровизации в процессе творчества будущего педагога / Е. Б. Мягкая. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 42 (332). — С. 55-57.
3. Ro'ziyeva D.I., Tolipov O'.Q. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogic mahorat. –T.: Innovatsiya-ziyo, 2019.
4. Ходжайев В.Х. Umumiy pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyoti. Darslik –T.: Sano-standart, 2017.-
5. Харькин В.Н. Педагогическая импровизация: теория и методика. М., 1992 г. - 264с.
6. Харькин В.Н., Импровизация... Импровизация? Импровизация!. Магистр, 1997 г., - 288 с.
7. Щербакова Т. Н. Импровизация как компонент творчества современного педагога — // Педагогическое мастерство : материалы IV Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Москва, февраль 2014 г.). — Москва : Буки-Веди, 2014. — С. 13-16. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/100/5010/>